

CASSAVA POST-HARVEST LOSSES AND FOOD SECURITY IN IDOMA LAND, NIGERIA: EXAMINING FARMERS' COPING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

Cassava is a vital staple crop in Idoma land, Benue State, where it plays a central role in household food supply, income generation, and rural livelihoods. However, substantial post-harvest losses threaten the benefits of cassava farming, reducing the quantity available for consumption, sale, or processing into key by-products like gari, akpu, flour and cassava chips. This study examined the extent of cassava post-harvest losses, their effects on household food security, and identified the coping strategies adopted by farmers. Data collected for this study were analyzed using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. Qualitative data were employed to choose 394 cassava farmers across selected communities. Findings revealed that the highest losses occurred during processing and storage stages, accounting for over 40% of the total post-harvest losses. These losses directly reduced household food availability, limited income from sales, and disrupted the supply of major cassava-based foods. In response, farmers adopted local coping strategies such as immediate processing after harvest, sun-drying, and the use of traditional storage facilities. While these methods helped to slow spoilage, they were often inadequate during peak harvest periods when processing capacities were overwhelmed. The study concludes that reducing cassava post-harvest losses is critical for strengthening household food security in Idoma land. It recommends investment in improved processing and storage infrastructure, capacity-building for farmers on modern post-harvest techniques, and the promotion of value-added cassava products to reduce waste and boost income. These interventions are essential for enhancing resilience and food system stability in rural Idoma communities that depend heavily on cassava.

Keywords: *Cassava, Post-harvest losses, Household food security, Smallholder farmers, Coping strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is a major pillar of food security and rural livelihood in Nigeria, particularly in Idoma land, Benue State, where it functions as both a staple food and a source of income (Adeoti, Fapojuwo, & Olowu, 2021; IITA, 2022). Its ability to thrive in diverse soil types, resist drought, and require minimal input has made it a widely cultivated crop among smallholder farmers. Cassava's processed forms, such as *gari*, *akpu*, flour, and chips, not only ensure food availability but also support household economies through local trade (Yusuf & Okoye, 2023).

Despite its importance, the benefits of cassava cultivation are significantly reduced by post-harvest losses, primarily due to the crop's high perishability. Without prompt processing, ideally within 48 to 72 hours after harvest, cassava roots rapidly deteriorate, especially in humid climates (FAO, 2023; Oluwole & Adebayo, 2020). In rural areas like Idoma land, where access to efficient processing, storage, and transportation infrastructure remains limited, these losses translate into lost food, income, and labour for already vulnerable households (Agbonlahor, Okoruwa, & Ogundele, 2022).

These post-harvest losses exacerbate food insecurity by reducing the volume of food available for consumption and undermining income generation from processed products. The impact is particularly harsh on low-income farming households, where livelihood options are limited and food prices continue to rise. In response, farmers often resort to coping mechanisms such as early harvesting, immediate conversion into *gari* or *akpu*, sun-drying, and traditional storage methods. However, these strategies are often constrained by inadequate processing

equipment, a lack of preservation technologies, and insufficient technical knowledge (Onyenwigwe, Umeh, & Nwaobiala, 2018; Ijeoma, Eze, & Nwosu, 2022).

This study examines the scale of cassava post-harvest losses in Idoma land and their implications for household food security. It also assesses indigenous coping practices and explores potential avenues for improving post-harvest handling. The findings aim to inform interventions that can strengthen cassava-based farming systems, enhance food availability, and reduce poverty in rural Nigeria (Ezedinma, Sanni, & Adeniji, 2022; Okpukpara, Ugwumba, & Nwalieji, 2022).

Cassava remains a vital food security crop in sub-Saharan Africa due to its resilience, adaptability to marginal soils, and high carbohydrate yield. In Nigeria, the world's largest cassava producer, it serves not only as a staple food but also as a key economic commodity, processed into products like *gari*, *akpu*, *fufu*, and cassava chips. However, a significant proportion of harvested cassava never reaches consumers due to post-harvest losses, posing a major threat to food security, especially in rural areas such as Idoma land. The tuber's high moisture content makes it extremely perishable, deteriorating within 48 to 72 hours if not promptly processed (Oduro et al., 2020). This rapid spoilage is compounded by infrastructural deficits such as poor roads, limited access to preservation technologies, inadequate processing capacity, and minimal extension services, challenges particularly acute in rural farming communities (Affognon et al., 2015).

These losses compromise food availability and accessibility, two of the four pillars of food security identified by FAO (2013). In

cassava-dependent communities, disruptions in availability often translate into temporary food shortages, reduced dietary diversity, and income loss. Ikuenobe and Ayoola (2019) point out that cassava losses occur not only on the farm but across transportation, processing, packaging, and marketing stages, driven by both labour constraints and systemic issues like market inaccessibility and lack of equipment.

Farmers' responses to these losses vary.

While some adopt reactive coping strategies such as early harvesting, small-scale *gari* production, or distress sales, these are often inadequate and unsustainable in the long term. The effectiveness of such coping mechanisms is influenced by factors including household income, gender roles, and access to community support networks. As Okafor et al. (2021) note, farmers linked to cooperatives or shared processing centres fare better in reducing losses.

Despite broad national studies, there remains a lack of localized empirical research exploring how smallholder farmers in specific cultural and agro-ecological contexts like Idoma land experience and manage post-harvest losses. This study addresses that gap by investigating the lived realities of cassava farmers in the region, examining how these losses affect household food supply, and documenting the coping mechanisms employed at the grassroots level

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Idoma land, southern Benue State, Nigeria, covering

four purposively selected LGAs—Otukpo, Ohimini, Okpokwu, and Ogbadibo, based on high cassava production. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select cassava-farming households across eight communities. Data collection combined quantitative and qualitative approaches. Structured questionnaires captured information on post-harvest losses, coping strategies, and food security dimensions (availability, accessibility, and consumption adequacy). Additionally, Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were held with farmers, processors, and extension officers to enrich contextual understanding. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 28, with descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were thematically analyzed to identify patterns in post-harvest loss management and its impact on household food security.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Understanding the socio-demographic profile of cassava farmers in Idoma land is essential for interpreting post-harvest loss patterns and their implications for household food security. The majority of respondents were male (61%), with most falling within the economically active age range of 31–50 years (54%) (Table 1). Educational attainment was relatively high, with 77% having at least primary education. Christianity was the dominant religion (91%), reflecting the region's religious makeup. Most respondents had less than 20 years of farming experience (82%), indicating a mix of emerging and

moderately experienced farmers.

Commercial-scale farming was practised by 57% of the sample, while 43% operated at the subsistence level. Farm sizes were generally small, with 76% cultivating less than 2 hectares. Annual income levels were modest; 86% earned less than ₦300,000, underscoring the economic vulnerability of

many cassava-farming households. These socio-economic characteristics highlight critical constraints, limited land access, low income, and moderate farming experience, which shape farmers' capacity to manage post-harvest losses effectively and sustain food security.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Attributes of the Respondents (n = 394)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	239	61
Female	155	39
Marital Status		
Married	157	40
Divorced	129	33
Widowed	51	13
Single	35	9
Separated	22	5
Age		
Below 30	66	17
31–40	92	24
41–50	121	30
51–60	72	19
61 and above	43	10
Educational Level		
No Formal Education		
Primary Education	32	8.2
Secondary Education	130	33.3
Tertiary Education	172	44.1
	60	14.4
Religion		
Christianity	357	91
Islam	14	4
Traditional	23	5
Farming Experience		
Below 10 years	164	41
10–20 years	159	41
21–30 years	63	16
31 years and above	8	2

Scale of Farming

Subsistence Scale	169	43
Commercial	225	57

Farm Size

Less than 0.5 hectare	38	10
0.5 –1 hectare	118	30
1 –2 hectares	183	46
2 –3 hectares	41	10
3 –4 hectares	13	3
4 –5 hectares	1	1

Estimated Annual Income

Less than ₦50,000	24	6
₦50,000 – ₦100,000	87	21
₦101,000 – ₦200,000	160	41
₦201,000 – ₦300,000	93	24
₦301,000 and above	30	8
Total	394	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Data collected from 394 cassava farmers across the seven local government areas of Idoma land revealed significant post-harvest losses amounting to approximately 78,800 kilograms over three years (2020–2023). These losses pose a serious threat to household food security and income for smallholder farmers who depend heavily on cassava production. The processing stage recorded the most substantial losses, accounting for 23,640 kg or 33% of the total (Table 2). This was largely attributed to the perishable nature of cassava tubers, which begin to deteriorate within 24 to 48 hours of harvest. Farmers reported that delays caused by limited access to functional processing equipment were a major contributor. Most rely on rented machines that are either unavailable or frequently break down, forcing them to fall back on slow, manual processing.

Table 2: Estimated Cassava Post-Harvest Losses among Farmers from June 2020 to June 2023 in Idoma Land

Stages of Cassava PHL	of Mean (100kg bags per household)	LossEstimated Total Loss (kg)	Frequency (n = 394)	Percentage (%)
Losses at Harvest	197	19,700	110	28
Gathering and Transportation	79	7,880	60	15
Processing (Gari, Akpu, Chips)	236	23,640	130	33
Storage	118	11,820	40	10
Packaging	59	5,910	20	5
Marketing	99	9,850	34	9
Total	788	78,800	394	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

One female processor in Ohimini, during a key informant interview (KII), shared: *"If you harvest today and do not start work immediately, the tubers spoils fasert. I have lost a lot when the machine we usually rent was unavailable, sometimes available but broken down from lack of spare parts"* This supports findings by FAO (2023) and Oluwole & Adebayo (2020), who identified equipment bottlenecks as a leading cause of cassava losses across West Africa. Within the processing stage, gari production suffered the greatest loss at 9,850 kg reported by 85 farmers, followed by akpu (7,880 kg) and cassava chips (5,910 kg). The vulnerability of gari was linked to its complex, time-sensitive processing stages, where delays in grating, fermenting, dewatering, or roasting can easily lead to the change of color and spoilage.

A key informant from Otukpa in Ogbadibo emphasized the challenge: *"Sometimes you will grate and ferment the cassava, but rain will not allow it to dry. Other times, the roasting machine will fail, and all your effort will be wasted. Gari production is risky if everything is not ready"* The absence of propagating platforms and weatherproof facilities, especially during the rainy season, contributes significantly to these losses. Harvest-stage losses were the second highest, with 19,700 kg lost by 110 farmers (28%). Although harvesting appears straightforward, farmers face multiple challenges, especially labour shortages during peak harvest seasons. Delays often result in tubers remaining in the soil past their optimal maturity, leading to decay and lignification. This significantly reduces both yield and processing quality.

A farmer in Ogbadibo described the situation: *harvesting the cassava, laborers are not available. And when you delay too long, the cassava gets too mature and starts to rot in the ground.*” Additionally, the use of pre-harvest herbicides close to harvesting was reported by some respondents to contribute to spoilage, as chemical residues disrupt moisture balance and microbial resistance. This observation aligns with the findings of Adeoti, Fapojuwo, and Olowu (2021), who noted that herbicide residues shorten cassava's post-harvest shelf life. The gathering and transportation stage was another area of concern, accounting for 7,880 kg (15%) of total losses. Farmers often rely on motorbikes or wheelbarrows to move cassava from the farm to their homes or processing points. Rough rural roads and poor transport conditions cause physical damage to tubers, hastening spoilage.

As one respondent from Otukpo explained: *“We load cassava on bikes or wheelbarrows, and it gets crushed or soaked if it rains. Once it stays overnight, these spoiling intensify cassava's already narrow post-harvest window and increase the risk of microbial decay. Storage-related losses were also significant, with 11,820 kg lost, mostly due to the lack of proper storage facilities. Farmers often store peeled or grated cassava products for several days while waiting for market days or access to processors. Without adequate ventilation or temperature control, these products are exposed to mould, heat damage, and rodent infestation. This finding is consistent with Ijeoma et al. (2022), who reported that storage gaps contribute to rural food insecurity.*

At the packaging and marketing stages, losses were reported at 5,910 kg and 9,850 kg respectively. Although smaller in quantity, these losses are critical in terms of value leakage. Farmers mentioned that poorly packaged cassava products, particularly akpu and gari, tend to spoil when not sold quickly due to delayed market access or unfavorable weather. A respondent from Adoka Ehaje remarked: *“If you don't sell on market day, and it stays till the following week, it begins to spoil.”* ~~Especially the storage, cassava (akpu) of~~ market infrastructure, and weak transport linkages between rural and urban markets were key contributors to these issues. This is supported by Ezedinma, Sanni, and Adeniji (2022), who documented similar losses tied to weak market chains. Altogether, the widespread and multi-stage nature of cassava losses in Idoma land reflects deep-rooted weaknesses in post-harvest management. These losses are not merely technical but also systemic, undermining both food availability and household income. The consistent narratives from key informants reflect that while farmers are aware of the problems, they lack the infrastructure, financial resources, and technical training to effectively reduce the losses. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated mix of policy and grassroots interventions. Solutions such as mobile processing units, cooperative storage systems, improved rural road networks, and practical training in post-harvest handling are urgently needed. As noted by Onyenwigwe et al. (2018), sustainable improvements in rural food systems depend on community-led innovations supported by institutional frameworks.

Effects of Cassava Post-Harvest Losses on Household Food Security in Idoma Land

The implications of cassava post-harvest losses (PHL) on food security in Idoma land are both direct and multidimensional, affecting the availability and accessibility of food for households that depend heavily on cassava as a staple and as a source of income. As shown in Table 3, the data collected from 394 cassava-farming households underscore the far-reaching impact of these losses on food consumption patterns, local market supply, and affordability in the region.

. Effects on Food Availability: Losses of Staple Stock and Local Supply Chains

Cassava post-harvest losses in Idoma land have significantly affected food availability, with 105 respondents (26%) indicating that spoilage after harvest reduced what was left for family consumption (Table 3). These losses mostly occur when tubers are not processed quickly enough, as cassava begins to deteriorate within 48 hours after harvesting. Delays often stem from a lack of processing equipment or drying facilities. A respondent in Otukpo explained: *“My children sometimes eat gari with only pepper soup with virtually nothing in it for days when we lose much of our cassava before we even finish processing. The farm gave us plenty, but what we ended up with, wasn't even enough.”*

Table 3: Effects of Post-Harvest Losses of Cassava on Food Security in Idoma Land

Effects	Freq uency	Percentage (%)
Availability		
Insufficient cassava products for hou sehold consumption	105	26
Limited cassava products reaching markets, reducing available food	89	22
Overdependence on other foodstuff, especially imported ones	50	13
Loss of cassava reduces incom e, limits ability to buy food	66	16
Poor storage leads to spoilage, reducing food availability	50	13

Accessibility		
Higher cassava prices make food unaffordable	10	3
Transportation problems reduce markets access, leading to PHL	5	1
Income loss limits food purchasing ability	10	3
Spoilage reduces cassava accessibility in local markets	3	1
Poorer households struggle with reduced food supply	6	2
Total	394	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Despite having good yields, households often face scarcity due to the inability to preserve or process what they harvest. Related to this is the decline in available cassava products in local markets, as 89 respondents (22%) noted, even when cassava is grown, post-harvest losses in processing, drying, or storage limit supply to markets. Many farmers depend on outdated or unavailable equipment, and drying is disrupted by rain or contamination. A female farmer in Ogbadibo recounted: *“There are times when gari will be so scarce in the market, because most families lost most part of their cassava, to one problem or the other, so even the ones available for sale are costly and not even properly processed.”* Such market shortages reflect community-level breakdowns in the local food chain. As a result, 50 respondents (13%) reported relying more on non-local or imported

staples like rice and noodles. This trend undermines local food systems and raises food costs, especially for rural families. The effect goes beyond nutrition; it challenges household food sovereignty and exposes families to market shocks.

Income loss further limits food access. 66 respondents (16%) said that when cassava spoils, they lack funds to purchase other food items. A male farmer from Okpokwu noted: *gari we suppose bills on left over five bags. We managed with only what we could afford outside cassava products against our preference.* reaction; cassava spoilage prevents income generation, which in turn limits dietary variety and quantity. Poor storage facilities worsen this problem. 50 respondents (13%) complained of inadequate drying platforms, pest attacks, and spoilage of products like akpu and gari. When not

properly pressed or stored, akpu ferments too much and becomes unfit for consumption.

A farmer in Otukpa shared:

the akpu, if there is no clean water to keep it or the weather is too hot, by the next day it

This supports FAO

(2023), which links poor post-processing storage with food insecurity in vulnerable communities. Food accessibility was also negatively impacted. Furthermore, 10 respondents (3%) reported that rising cassava prices made even basic foods unaffordable. As losses reduced supply, prices for gari and other derivatives increased. A widow from Odudaje in Otukpa LGA lamented: *“The cassava I lost in March would have bought me a bag or two of rice for our home use, but now I buy half tin only. Even my grandchildren go to bed hungry sometimes.”*

Post-harvest losses also undermine cassava's role as a tradable good, as 10 respondents (3%) said they couldn't afford other foods due to cassava spoilage, when they lose the chance to sell cassava products, their access to protein-rich foods like beans and vegetables declines.

Transportation challenges added to the burden. Meanwhile, 5 respondents (1%) explained that due to bad roads and poor access to transport, harvested cassava often spoiled before reaching markets. As one farmer in Ojugo explained: *“If you harvest and cannot move it quickly, you just lose everything. The cassava will start to spoil even before you reach the market.”* (2021) In addition, poor rural infrastructure hampers food distribution and market integration. Some (1%) also mentioned that rain and humidity during wet seasons ruined already processed gari,

making it moldy and unacceptable to buyers. Finally, 6 respondents (2%) stressed how community-wide losses lead to a breakdown in mutual support. When all families are affected, even informal sharing and assistance collapse. As one informant from Ogene Otukpa put it: *“When cassava fails for one, others help. But when it fails for many, everyone is hungry.”* This highlights the communal nature of food security in rural areas. When cassava losses affect many households at once, the entire safety net crumbles.

Overall, the evidence from Table 3 shows that cassava post-harvest losses in Idoma land deeply affect both the availability and accessibility of food. Physical loss of produce, high processing failure, and poor storage reduce what families can eat or sell, while income loss and price hikes limit their ability to purchase other food. These losses are not isolated, they reflect systemic gaps that leave farming households more vulnerable to hunger and malnutrition. Addressing them will require investment in rural infrastructure, modern processing tools, community storage systems, and better access to markets.

Figure 1 shows that post-harvest losses of cassava in Idoma land affect food availability (90%) more than accessibility (10%). Key issues include insufficient household supply (26%), limited market presence (22%), and income loss (16%), all linked to spoilage during processing and storage. Other effects include reliance on imported foods and poor-quality storage. Though fewer, access issues like price hikes and transport delays still threaten vulnerable households. These results stress the need for improved processing and infrastructure.

Figure 1: A pie chart on the effect of cassava post-harvest losses on food security in Idoma land
 Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

The data in Table 4 reveal that cassava farmers in Idoma land apply several coping and preventive strategies against post-harvest losses, but these measures are sporadic, weakly adopted, and often implemented in isolation. This scattered approach contributes to the persistence of losses across the cassava value chain. At the harvest level, 17% of farmers reported harvesting at the appropriate maturity stage, but only 11.2% had adequate labor, and just 2% practiced gleaning. This reflects ongoing labor constraints, with many farmers unable to harvest efficiently or promptly.

Table 4: Strategies to Curtail Post-Harvest Losses of Cassava at different levels

Strategies to Curtail Post-Harvest Losses of Cassava		F=394	100 %
Farm Level	Proper gleaning to recover leftover cassava tubers	8	2.0
	Harvesting cassava at maturity to reduce losses	67	17.0
	Getting enough laborers to avoid delays and losses	44	11.2
Transportation Level	Adequate transport arrangement to reduce spoilage	19	4.8
	Minimizing transport delays	53	13.5
	Avoiding overloading during transport	61	15.5
	Maintaining access roads to cassava farms	14	3.6
Processing Level	Durable means of transport	12	3.0
	Hiring sufficient laborers to fast-track processing	18	4.6
	Ensuring all processing equipment are functional	21	5.3
	Personal supervision to reduce carelessness and waste	36	9.1
	Ensuring workers' commitment during processing	20	5.1
Storage Level	Early commencement of processing to avoid night work	11	2.8
	Proper maintenance of storage areas	24	6.1
	Proper drying of products before storage	38	9.6
	Spraying insecticides in storage facilities	5	1.3
Marketing Level	Seeking better market outlets	25	6.4
	Early market arrangements to reduce delays	32	8.1
	Monitoring market demand to avoid over supply	20	5.1

Source: field work, 2023

A farmer in Ogbadibo expressed: *“When you harvest alone or with few hands, you cannot finish in one day... That's how transported-related strategies were also minimal. Though 15.5% avoided overloading and 13.5% tried to minimize delays, only 4.8% arranged transport in advance, and a mere 3.6% used durable means or maintained roads. Another farmer from Okpoga stated: “Sometimes, the road from the farm cuts off when it rains... so many tubers have fallen off, bruised or cracked.”* Processing practices were also poorly adopted, with only 5.3% checking

equipment, 4.6% hiring adequate labor, and 9.1% supervising for quality. As a female processor in Idekpa reported:

“you're in the middle of grating and the engine breaks down... Then they begin to spoil and change colour.”

Storage practices were similarly low: 9.6% dried products properly, 6.1% maintained storage spaces, and only 1.3% used pest control. A farmer recounted: *“Once the sacks are wet or rats enter the store, destruction begins... You have to sell it fast or lose everything.”* At the marketing

level, 8.1% made early arrangements, 6.4% sought new markets, and 5.1% monitored demand, all pointing to limited use of market intelligence or coordinated sales. Another farmer from Ohimini explained: *“If you don't plan for market ahead... the gari will become stale and change color and customers will reject it from the odour.”*

These findings highlight that while farmers are aware of good practices, lack of integration, planning, and infrastructure severely limits their effectiveness. Losses persist because strategies are inconsistently applied, not preventive, and undermined by systemic issues like labor shortages, poor roads, limited access to mechanization, and uncoordinated markets. An extension officer in Otukpa added: *“We tell them how to reduce losses, but many are not organized in cooperatives... so we cannot reach them effectively.”* This underscores that effective coping strategies must be scaled, institutionalized, and supported by training, cooperative networks, and rural investment.

In conclusion, current farmer efforts in Idoma land reflect isolated attempts that lack support systems. Until coordinated action is taken, through policy, infrastructure, and cooperative support, post-harvest losses will remain widespread, even where knowledge exists.

Why Losses Persist Despite These Strategies

From the evidence above, it becomes clear that post-harvest losses persist not because there are no strategies, but because: The strategies are not widely adopted or practiced consistently. There is no integration across stages of the supply

chain; most farmers rely on one or two isolated interventions. Reactive actions dominate over preventive planning; many only act when spoilage has already begun or when crises (like rain) force them to adjust. Systemic barriers, like poor rural roads, labor shortages, lack of mechanization, and market constraints, continue to undermine individual efforts. This position is echoed by Oluwole and Adebayo (2020), who noted that without institutional reforms and community-level capacity building, scattered individual strategies will remain insufficient to tackle post-harvest losses meaningfully.

As an extension officer in Otukpa shared:

“We tell them how to reduce losses, but many are not organized in cooperatives. So, most times, we cannot reach them effectively.” This emphasizes that for coping strategies to work; they must be institutionalized, scaled, and supported with extension training, infrastructure, and access to affordable tools. Without these, farmers' current efforts will remain like patches over a leaking roof, visible but ultimately ineffective.

In conclusion, the coping strategies observed among cassava farmers in Idoma land reflect good intentions but inadequate execution. The efforts are fragmented, often reactive, and suffer from poor coordination and weak infrastructural support. Until farmers are backed by robust extension services, functional storage and processing infrastructure, durable transport systems, and better-organized markets, post-harvest losses will persist, even in the presence of knowledge or strategies. Policy interventions must therefore shift from simply promoting awareness to building systems that enable adoption, scale good practices, and institutionalize solutions that are currently practiced in isolation.

Comparative Perspective with Other Regions

The pattern of cassava post-harvest losses (PHL) in Idoma land reflects trends observed across cassava-producing communities in Africa, though distinct contextual differences persist. This study recorded losses totaling 78,800 kg over three years, with the bulk occurring at the processing and harvesting stages. Comparable losses of 30–40% have been reported in southern Nigeria and parts of Ghana, attributed to delayed processing and inadequate storage (Awoyinka, 2009; Amoah *et al.*, 2020).

In eastern Uganda, efforts to process cassava into flour within 48 hours of harvest reduce spoilage, yet the absence of decentralized processing centers, also evident in Idoma land, continue to compromise product quality (Nakabonge *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, western Tanzania has demonstrated the success of structured interventions, such as farmer training and collective bulking centers, which have reduced losses and improved incomes (FAO, 2023). These contrasts highlight the critical role of institutional frameworks, market linkages, and community coordination in mitigating PHL.

Idoma land, however, reflects low uptake of such structured strategies. Coping mechanisms remain largely reactive and individual-based, hampered by poor infrastructure, weak cooperative presence, and lack of mechanization. These challenges are common across many parts of sub-Saharan Africa, but their intensity and local responses vary, shaped by governance structures and development priorities (Adenegan *et al.*, 2021). Bridging this gap in Idoma land will require context-specific innovations informed by successful regional models.

CONCLUSION

This study establishes that cassava post-harvest losses in Idoma land, particularly during processing, harvesting, transportation, and

storage, significantly threaten household food security. With over 78,800 kg lost between 2020 and 2023, processing delays, equipment inefficiencies, and inadequate storage were the major contributors, especially affecting gari, akpu, and chips. These losses directly reduced food availability and accessibility, while also limiting farmers' income and capacity to afford alternative food sources. Although some coping strategies exist, they remain largely informal, reactive, and poorly coordinated. Structural constraints, such as limited infrastructure and weak extension support, further exacerbate the problem. Ultimately, these losses undermine cassava's role as a key livelihood and food security asset in the study area, highlighting an urgent need for integrated, systemic interventions.

Recommendations

To address cassava post-harvest losses in Idoma land, this study proposes the following targeted interventions:

- i. Mechanized Processing and Storage
Providing small-scale cassava-processing machines and affordable storage facilities will reduce delays, limit spoilage, and improve the shelf-life of products like *gari* and *akpu*.
- ii. Farmer Cooperatives and Collective Efforts
Strengthening cooperatives will enhance farmers' access to shared labour, equipment, and markets, enabling more efficient harvesting and processing.
- iii. Training and Capacity Development
Periodic training on improved harvesting, drying, and packaging techniques will help farmers reduce losses and adopt better post-harvest practices.
- iv. Infrastructure and Policy Support
Upgrading rural roads and integrating PHL reduction into agricultural policy will ease market access and ensure broader compliance with improved handling standards.

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